

The Diplomatic Networks of Ancient Athens: The Evidence from the Decrees

Silvan Auf Der Maur [1]

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This study combines attempts to expand on the traditional scholarship around Athenian diplomacy by systematically evaluating the extensive corpus of decrees which were passed by the Athenian assembly to reconstruct the diplomatic network of the ancient city state and observe how it shifted over time.

The decrees of the Athenian assemblies have been painstakingly collected, transcribed and translated by scholars and are published as the *Inscriptiones Graecae*, a project by the University of Berlin-Brandenburg (Hallos et al. 2001).

These decrees have the ability to yield considerable insight into the political networks within Greece, a topic for which they have not yet been systematically used. While there has been a growing interest and awareness of the importance of networks of interaction in the ancient world, as shown by ground-breaking new approaches such as that of Irad Malkin, these perspectives are still developing in the field of ancient history and have rarely been applied to specific, empirically based case studies (Malkin, 2013). As such, this paper will seek to fill this gap in the current state of the field on Athenian decrees and answer the question: What can decrees tell us about ancient Athenian diplomatic networks in Greece? Understanding how the political institutions of Athens determined their diplomatic focus, and how they put it into practice is of crucial relevance in order to assess whether the Athenian state had a coordinated foreign policy and what role decrees played in this process.

A select number of decrees which were passed by the Athenian *demoi*, refer specifically to other locations in Greece, indicating that they may be of relevance to the study of diplomatic networks. By visualizing these geographically specific decrees, a networked view of diplomatic decrees and the various city states or regions they referred to is created, providing a geographical picture of the transnational connections of the Athenian state.

This dataset of over a hundred decrees consists of various forms of diplomatic pacts, as well as honorific decrees, bestowing honors on politically influential individuals from foreign cities, as well as honoring certain individuals with the role of proxenos, which served as a sort of ambassador who was trusted to represent the interests of Athens in their home city. These various kinds of decree are categorized, dated and mapped to provide a visual representation of the extent of the Athenian diplomatic network and its evolution.

For the purposes of this study, Athenian diplomatic history is divided into two distinct periods, for each of which a separate network is constructed. The first period begins with the first documented finds of decrees of relevance to diplomacy, in 456 BCE, and continues until the decisive end of the Peloponnesian war in 404 BCE, which made for a clear break in Athenian political history, as an oligarchic government was temporarily imposed on the city. (Krentz, 1982) The second period will pick up from this temporary loss of sovereignty and track the recovery of the Athenians until their second major defeat in 338 BCE at the hands of the Macedonians.

These periods each ended with transformative changes both for Athens and for Greek diplomacy at large and are therefore useful periods to track the shifts and developments of the institution of diplomacy in Athens. These clear upheavals provide a means of comparing the traditional historical narratives promulgated by ancient authors to the picture which emerges from the analysis of the decrees. This study shows, that these shifts are also reflected in the decrees, which display a shifting distribution of diplomatic pacts, in line with the historical narratives.

The decrees, however, go beyond the narratives told by later historians and show other developments which may not have drawn the attention of those scholars. This may be due to the lack of historical consequence some of these decrees ended up having, but at times it is also due to the narrow focus on specific conflicts or developments which do not encompass the full complexity of Athenian foreign policy. The decrees reveal, for example, the ties which Athens cultivated with cities and citizens throughout the Mediterranean and they also show the overarching developments in how diplomacy was conducted. The dominance of Leagues, while widely acknowledged in scholarship, is clearly emphasized when looking at the evidence of the decrees. The consequences the further entrenchment of these federal entities had also become clear, such as the disappearance of non-aggression pacts in favor of outright alliances. Most importantly however, the decrees demonstrate how an ancient society was able to decide on foreign policy collectively through democratic institutions, and that this process resulted in a coherent and intelligent strategy which responded and adapted dynamically to a continually shifting diplomatic landscape.

**All Athenian State Connections
In Greece 456-404 B.C.E.**

An in-depth source analysis of the decrees also provides insight into the biases inherent in analyzing large historical datasets, such as the survivorship bias which led to the preservation of certain decrees over others. The field of ancient history is familiar with these limitations, due to their severity in the sparse material and textual record of these periods, but the lessons learned from such an analysis are crucial for all attempts at constructing networks of historical actors and through the more extreme case of this ancient example, other practitioners of historical network analysis could be sensitised to the limitations of their data as well.

References

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